

OPEN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH ASSESSMENT AT SOFIA UNIVERSITY “ST. KLIMENT OHRIDSKI”

INTERIM REPORT

Focusing on the Legal Framework Analysis, Desk Research, Focus Groups, and Silent Client

Methodology

Institution: Sofia University “St. Kliment Ohridski”

Date: 1st June 2025

DISCLAIMER: PLEASE NOTE THAT THIS IS A PRELIMINARY REPORT FROM AN ONGOING STUDY WHICH WILL BE UPDATED BY OCTOBER 2025 BY THE PROJECT TEAM.

METHODOLOGY

Our study combines several methods, chosen to provide an opportunity for a better understanding of the current state of integrating open science aspects into research assessment. Both open science and contribution to CoARA are still underdeveloped in Bulgaria. The country has only one CoARA signatory.

The mixed methods applied within AURA include:

- Selection and comprehensive analysis of the gaps and misalignment among legislative documents. This analysis was aimed at identifying key requirements towards research assessment, the presence of any open science-related aspects and exploring to what extent they are implemented in research evaluation. Although the project addresses institutional change, the institutional assessment practices are aligned to national legal framework which required to widen the scope of this study component.
- Focus groups aimed at gathering opinions which would help to understand the current level of engagement and hindering blocks across researchers, administration and policy makers.
- Secret shopper interviews allowing to engage deeper in the role of project office and understanding of evaluation within this key administrative structure providing project support. The choice of this unit was made taking into consideration that EU projects have a clear requirement for identifying open science components while this is not the case with other funders.

The following section provides an initial summary of the findings.

The national and institutional legal framework were analysed, taking into consideration also relevant EU developments. The analysis was based on 26 legal documents and projects at the EU and global levels, 9 at the national level and 13 at the Sofia University level.

The AURA project explores opportunities to broaden the scope of research assessment by integrating the open research dimension into existing evaluation frameworks. As part of the project's deliverables, the legal analysis aims to map and critically assess the current legal framework governing research assessment and promotion procedures at both national and institutional levels. It also examines the potential for incorporating open research practices into these frameworks.

In Bulgaria, the rules and mechanisms for assessing individual researchers can be grouped into three main avenues: **(i) Academic career progression** includes the criteria applied in evaluating individual researchers seeking to obtain scientific degrees (e.g., PhD) or academic titles (e.g., assistant professor, associate professor, professor); **(ii) Institutional self-evaluation and attestation systems** involve the ongoing monitoring and evaluation of academic performance at the institutional level, conducted through internal review mechanisms; **(iii) Accreditation of research organizations** encompasses the accreditation of scientific fields and doctoral programs and is based on the evaluation of institutional research capacity and quality, including assessment of the academic output of individual researchers.

The legal analysis examines the current system of research assessment in Bulgaria through these three interconnected avenues in order to assess the existing criteria used to evaluate academic outputs and to identify opportunities for integrating open science principles into these frameworks.

1. Legal Framework for Academic Career Development

A core component of Bulgaria's legal infrastructure in this domain is the Law on the Development of the Academic Staff in the Republic of Bulgaria (ZRASRB). At the time of its initial adoption in 2010, it aimed to move from a centralised model of academic appointments and degree acquisition to one based on institutional autonomy and competitive standards. ZRASRB was last revised in December 2022.

This legislation defines Minimum National Requirements (MNRs) for candidates seeking to acquire scientific degrees (such as PhD) or to be appointed to academic positions (assistant, associate professor, full professor). These requirements are entirely based on quantifiable indicators, mostly related to publication- and citation-based metrics, such as: number of authored monographs; number of publications in indexed journals; number of book chapters; number of studies and/or

reviews; number of citations (excluding self-citations) in referred and indexed journals by other authors citing the candidate's publications.

The legal framework for academic career development is further complemented by an Implementing Regulation of the law (PPZRASRB), last revised in March 2025. Also, a public consultation is currently underway on a Draft Decree of the Council of Ministers amending the PPZRASRB, open until 30 June 2025. PPZRASRB sets the minimum national requirements for each scientific field and/or professional area for obtaining any academic degree or holding any academic position. They are based on a selected group of indicators from those listed in the law and are expressed as a minimum number of points that a candidate must achieve in accordance with their individual results on these indicators. This regulation designates indexing in Web of Science and Scopus as the sole criterion for recognizing journals in the context of research assessment.

It should be acknowledged, that the law and its regulations also allow for the inclusion of publications in non-indexed but peer-reviewed journals, assigning them lower point values to reflect their reduced international visibility. The National Center for Information and Documentation (NACID) is charged with maintaining both national registries: the list of Bulgarian journals indexed in international databases, but also the list of Bulgarian peer-reviewed journals.

The minimum national requirements (MNRs) established by law form the foundation for academic career advancement. While institutions may further specify or supplement these requirements through internal rules, they may not alter them. This principle is affirmed in Decision No. 11 of October 5, 2010, by the Constitutional Court in Case No. 13/2010, which held that it falls within the legislature's authority to define MNRs and regulate academic promotion procedures. Although institutions are permitted to adopt their own internal regulations, the power to set the binding minimum standards cannot be entirely delegated to them.

According to the Rules for the conditions and procedure for obtaining scientific degrees and occupying academic positions at Sofia University "St. Kliment Ohridski", last amended on 30.10.2024, there are additional requirements added for doctoral candidates in three professional fields: Physical Sciences, Law and Medicine. In these cases requirements are specific to the respective professional field and do not add substantial evaluation criteria that may be linked to science communication.

2. Institutional Self-Evaluation and Attestation Systems

In addition to national-level indicators, research organisations and universities are required to conduct periodic internal evaluations of individual researchers, known as attestations. These evaluations are central to the Updated National Research Strategy (2017–2030), which emphasises the need for performance monitoring and alignment with international standards. Attestation must occur at least once every five years for academic staff, and is designed to monitor: (i)

teaching effectiveness and curriculum development; (ii) scientific output and publication quality; (iii) participation in institutional life and scientific governance and (iv) student evaluations and peer recognition.

The system for attesting researchers is regulated in Articles 120 - 126 of the Rules for the Structure and Activity of Sofia University "St. Kliment Ohridski" (PUDSU), last amended and supplemented on November 27, 2024, effective from December 16, 2024, and in the Quality Manual of Sofia University. The adopted system is permanent and is mandatorily applied every year by all faculties and for all lecturers. The criteria for attestation are determined by the Faculty Council (Department Council) according to the specifics of the respective structural unit based on the model criteria adopted by the Academic Council.

The criteria for the attestation of research activity are the following: (i) scientific publications in specialised scientific journals; (ii) popular publications; (iii) participation in international cooperation projects in scientific research; (iv) participation in university, national, and international scientific projects and events; (v) awards (national and international). Although not as rigid as the national career development metrics, criteria are still mostly quantitative and publication-based.

According to PUDSU, is permitted, by decision of the respective Faculty Council (Department Council), for the personal report form of the researcher to be supplemented in a way that reflects the specifics of the faculty (department), while observing the ratios foreseen in the standard for the weighting of the individual reported activities (Appendix 4.3 of the Quality Manual of Sofia University – Procedure for Attestation of Lecturers at Sofia University "St. Kliment Ohridski," item 3). Changes to the indicators may only be substantive – specification, addition, replacement – but changes to the point values are not allowed.

3. Accreditation of Research Organizations and Doctoral Programs

External evaluation of universities and research institutions is carried out by the National Evaluation and Accreditation Agency (NEAA), which employs criteria based on the European Standards and Guidelines (ESG). Accreditation procedures evaluate the University's scientific achievements, research capacity, and international reputation. Part of this assessment is based on the individual output of affiliated researchers. While not solely focused on individual researchers, this monitoring creates pressure on research organizations to ensure measurable results from their affiliated researchers.

Indicators are disaggregated by academic area and include metrics such as the average number of WoS/Scopus publications per faculty member, participation in national and international projects, and the citation index of the academic staff. Quantitative indicators for evaluating individual researcher activity include: (i) average annual number of publications per lecturer in indexed

journals (Web of Science, Scopus); (ii) average annual number of publications per lecturer in journals indexed and peer-reviewed in databases specific to the scientific field (ACM Digital Library, AIS eLibrary, CEEOL, DOAJ, Earthdoc, EBSCO, EconLIT, eLIBRARY.RU, EMBASE, ERIH+, IEEE Xplore, JSTOR, MathSciNet, ProQuest, PubMed/MedLine, SAO/NASA Astrophysics Data System, Science Direct, Zentralblatt); (iii) average annual number of publications per lecturer in journals listed in NACID's national reference list; (iv) average annual number of publications per lecturer in non-peer-reviewed journals; (v) average annual number of peer-reviewed monographs per lecturer; (vi) average annual number of university or school textbooks published per lecturer, including electronic versions with ISBN; (vii) average citation index per lecturer in the respective scientific field etc.

4. Conclusions

In conclusion, the legal analysis suggests that the Bulgarian scientific evaluation framework is quite rigid, heavily reliant on quantitative metrics focused primarily on publications and citations. The use of specific indexing databases such as Web of Science and Scopus for scientometric assessments is firmly embedded in regulatory documents. This approach is legislatively mandated, leaving institutions limited flexibility to deviate from these metrics. Consequently, any meaningful reform of the current evaluation system would require engagement from policymakers at the highest levels, potentially involving national-level initiatives to drive legislative change.

Furthermore, in the context of external evaluation of universities and research institutions, research organisations have virtually no flexibility. The NEAA's assessments are strictly regulated and standardised, leaving little room for institutions to adapt or tailor evaluation criteria to their specific contexts or priorities or to integrate alternative measures, such as open research practices, within the formal evaluation process.

That being said, institutions do have some opportunities to incorporate open research into their assessment processes.

One option is to supplement the nationally mandated Minimum National Requirements (MNRs) with additional criteria. However, this is an unlikely avenue for reform, as research organisations may avoid imposing extra requirements on their affiliated researchers' career development that could potentially put them at a competitive disadvantage compared to other institutions.

The internal attestation procedures appear to offer the greatest potential for integrating open science metrics. At Sofia University, this could be implemented on two levels.

First, open science criteria could be included as a requirement for the evaluation of publications within the publications component. This would require an institutional decision and an amendment to the PUDSU. For example, Sofia University might mandate that all publications

considered for attestation be openly accessible. Considering Bulgaria's recent introduction of Se, this requirement would be feasible without imposing additional financial burdens on individual researchers regarding primary open access publication fees.

The second option is to introduce incentives for publishing in open access or sharing open research data within the third evaluation component, "participation in institutional life and scientific governance." This could be implemented at the faculty level, offering a more flexible approach. However, a comprehensive, institution-wide strategy would be preferable to ensure consistency and greater impact.

Lastly, A new rulebook for the Science Research Fund was introduced in June 2025, alongside a national program to encourage publication in reputable international journals and expand open access.

This analysis is helpful in identifying several problems, mostly caused by misalignment of different legal acts, which impact research assessment.

Open science, although declared an underlying principle within research, has not been properly integrated into the national legislation which defines the institutional regulations – this is a key area which needs a combined national and institutional reform.

In the next months of the project, our team will explore during subsequent events to what extent researchers are aware of these issues and what ways forward they see as most suitable for researcher-driven improvement of research assessment.

FOCUS GROUPS - SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

The focus groups with researchers from various scientific disciplines, policy makers, administrators and civil society were held as the second part of the online seminar and the first webinar, respectively on May 19 and June 18, 2025. 15 Bulgarian participants took part in the seminar and 47 Bulgarian participants in the first webinar. To boost the discussion and thinking they were preceded by a guest introductory talk followed by common introduction to the aim of the discussion, splitting the participants into three groups with guided moderators, each with 10 participants in the group, which discussed a different aspect, feeding back the conclusions of these groups and a common discussion. 15 Bulgarian participants took part in the seminar and 47 Bulgarian participants in the first webinar. The total Bulgarian participants in all focus groups was 62. The participants were divided on the following criteria:

- University administration and staff
- Researchers
- General public - citizens, NGOs

The participant explored the topics (e.g., awareness of policies, support systems) and key themes and quotes.

Suggestions from the groups were captured in a Padlet (https://padlet.com/milena_dobрева/aura-23k2v32ursfddgry) – the next illustrations shows a fragment of it (these are in Bulgarian).

Figure 1. A fragment from the padlet collecting opinions of participants in the focus groups

The emerging findings and recommendations on key aspects related to open science and research assessment are summarised in the following table. For the time being, we are unpacking components which are relevant to three types of stakeholders – researchers/academics, University management and the general public.

Themes	Researchers	University Management	Public	Recommendations
1. Awareness of Open Science & Research Assessment	Researchers show a high level of awareness about Open Research, mainly	University administrators, as well as managers of Open Research Infrastructures	Citizens and NGOs perceive Open Science as accessible, understandable,	Targeted campaigns for early-stage and experienced researchers to

<p>Principles</p>	<p>through experiences with open-access publications, open data, and educational resources. However, only a small fraction fully embrace the broader UNESCO definition of Open Research and its comprehensive elements.</p>	<p>demonstrate the highest level of understanding of Open Research in its entirety, as they are directly involved in policy-making and regulatory frameworks. However, they face difficulties in effectively communicating policies to researchers and the public.</p> <p>There is a PhD School, and it could serve as a good communication channel to distribute knowledge for OS - there are some initial signs of courses developed for PhD students.</p>	<p>and beneficial to daily life. However, their understanding is still fragmented, associating Open Research primarily with open-access publications and communication of scientific results. Citizens are also very confident they can contribute to research even without researchers' guidance.</p> <p>Limited knowledge of Citizens Science (CS)</p> <p>Citizens mostly used as data providers but not contributing to formulating research and analysing the results.</p>	<p>promote open science and the opportunities it offers for scientific and career development.</p>
<p>2. Open Science Incentives</p>	<p>There are no formal requirements in the department to publish open access, share data, or engage in citizen science, unless it is a</p>	<p>There is a Law and secondary legislation, but the documents and procedures have not aligned yet.</p>	<p>NGOs collaborate on projects with academics, but this is a relatively small part of the researchers' assessment.</p> <p>There are no formal procedures</p>	<p>Setting minimum requirements and a broad system of incentives for the assessment system (both at the national and institutional levels).</p>

	requirement on the EU projects.		in the University's assessment system for Citizen Science. There are many civic initiatives. Beautiful Science, Ratio, etc.	Co-creation process for OS requirements and incentives.
3. Motivation and Culture Related to Research Assessment	<p>Targeting influential journals for papers</p> <p>High dependencies of the publishers</p> <p>The motivation is based on enthusiasts, who are a limited number in the natural and mathematical disciplines, but are highly committed and pioneers in the field.</p> <p>Early-stage scientists are also motivated because they believe this is a good way to advance their careers.</p> <p>For the most part,</p>	<p>The University administration is conservative, rigid and relies on quantitative metrics because they are easily measurable, provable and non-biased.</p> <p>They have no motivation to introduce innovations if it is not a legal obligation, and yet there is a delay.</p> <p>Balance between commercialisation and public good</p> <p>University Ratings</p>	<p>There is a need for more scientific knowledge to refute fake news and disinformation.</p>	<p>Formalise the process through a bonus system for researchers, faculty, and universities, which is tied to specific financial incentives, additional material incentives, and awards.</p> <p>Recognise the contribution of scientists implementing open science through awards, specialisations, and the like.</p>

	<p>scientists believe that open science activities are often solitary, time-consuming, and do not yield quick or short-term benefits, both material and in terms of a scientific career.</p> <p>They fear that by publishing, their results and data will be stolen.</p>			
4. Support & Infrastructures	<p>Discussions exposed the strengths and weaknesses of the process – infrastructures are often lacking or not user friendly (difficult deposit of publications, complicated extraction of data on citations).</p> <p>Incentives that directly influence evaluation and career development, but not as an obligation, but as a bonus</p>	<p>There is a lack of an up-to-date green access university repository where researchers can upload their work. (there is an older installation which is currently out of use and other systems which capture publication details but not the actual publications).</p> <p>No unit would be responsible for horizontally coordinating the processes of open science at the University.</p>	<p>They have no information about what exactly citizen science is, despite having experience with such practices.</p> <p>There is no funding for such projects.</p> <p>There is no network of similar organisations from different scientific disciplines.</p>	<p>Infrastructures to support the process – university repository</p> <p>Creating an open science structure that monitors the implementation of the principles in the evaluation and attestation system.</p> <p>Citizen Science Platform</p>

5. Activities	<p>Joint discussion of the new criteria for open science, not to be imposed from above as an obligation, but rather as a bonus.</p> <p>Seminars, trainings, and mentoring on the individual principles and how they bring concrete benefits for their scientific and career development.</p>	<p>The problem of plagiarism is a serious issue that could be addressed through Open Peer Review.</p> <p>AI abuse</p> <p>Winning EU projects is directly dependent on data sharing.</p> <p>Enhancing the skills of academic staff leads to improved results and higher rankings for universities.</p>	<p>There is no place, event, or festival where you can meet, learn more, and share experiences.</p>	<p>Introducing bonus points for implementing open science in the researcher's attestation card.</p> <p>Developing programs to stimulate open science - awards, points, credits, mentoring, training courses.</p>

Researchers have a range of concerns around the way evaluation is made and it is clear open research still needs to be better integrated and positioned within research practice. Currently it does not contribute to assessment practice.

In the next months we will be offering possible scenarios for including open research in various assessment processes.

SECRET CLIENT STUDY

The Silent Client study was conducted with the Department of Projects and Science of Sofia University. This unit is responsible for tracking all submitted project proposals as well as supporting successful ones and deals with a wide range of donors with different requirements. The calls of Horizon are those with the most apparent demand and an allocated part of the submission forms to discuss open science. In the cases of national funding, this is just starting.

The following underdeveloped areas were identified:

- The relatively low knowledge of the concept of open science impacts the project planning where this component is either not taken into consideration or follows the lead of larger consortia in the case of Horizon projects.

- Evaluation is done retrospectively, after a project is finalised.
- When preparing project proposals, there is no connection between the evaluation of scientists and the design of the project. There is a criterion in the academic assessment which takes into consideration the amount of external funding they secured but there is nothing related to the efforts to design proposals and the open science components in those proposals.
- Good practices are mostly emerging when project proposals are discussed, which allows for an entry point to engage researchers.

This study mostly captures the perceptions of units which play a key role in supporting researchers. As they also are relevant to providing guidance on project opportunities, it is useful to establish how such a unit communicates aspects related to research assessment in relation to project work.

Research support offices are one of the university structures which could improve the connection between project work in particular – especially having in mind the various open research requirements of different funders. This is still an underused opportunity to expand the knowledge on opens science across researchers.

In the next months of the project, our team will explore how research offices can provide more robust guidance on open science.

CONCLUSIONS

Within these months, we started establishing the institutional practice related to research assessment and the opportunities to include open research into it, exploring the legal framework, opinions of researchers and the position of research support offices. On the next stage, we will consolidate these findings into a systematic thematic analysis, identify gaps which provide opportunities for intervention. We will present these initial findings to the national stakeholders – the Ministry of Education and Science and the National Evaluation and Accreditation Agency.

Acknowledgement. AURA: Advancing Sofia University St Kliment Ohridski's Research Assessment acknowledges the support of the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA); CoARA Boost project 24-CoARA-074.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. Funded within the framework of the CoARA Boost Project under grant agreement No 24-CoARA-074.